

INSTRUCTIONAL MODULE: ITS EFFECT ON STUDENTS' MATHEMATICS PERFORMANCE

Anelyn P. Montes, Ph.D., Harry R. Palmes, Ph.D.

*Calinog National Comprehensive High School, Department of Education,
Region VI, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This quasi-experimental study aimed at determining the effect of an instructional module on students' performance in mathematics of Grade 8 learners in a high school in the Municipality of Calinog, Province of Iloilo. The data were obtained through the use of a performance test and instructional module. The descriptive statistics used were frequency count and mean, while the Mann-Whitney U Test and Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test set at 0.05 alpha were used as inferential statistics. The findings revealed that there was no significant difference in the pre-test mathematics performance in between the control group and the experimental group. Both groups fell on the same category interpreted as "satisfactory". The study further revealed that in the post-test, the experimental group scored much higher than the control group. The group's performance shifted from "satisfactory" to "very satisfactory", after the group was given the intervention, which was the instructional module. It can be concluded from the results that, the instructional module is an effective tool in teaching mathematics which resulted in better performance of the students.

Keywords: *Instructional Module, Mathematics Performance, Effect*

INTRODUCTION

It's a well-known fact that mathematics is a tough and demanding subject, and that some individuals find it boring. Specifically, it is frequently perceived as challenging, confusing, and unpleasant to some individuals. There is a stigma

associated with mathematics, and those who are good at it are often treated as if they are perfectly normal. In addition to being useful for applying basic numeracy skills, mathematics is significant. It is also the most effective method for assisting pupils in developing higher-order cognitive skills and logical reasoning. Accordingly, one of the main goals of mathematics instruction is to help students develop a positive attitude toward the subject (Abalde and Oco, 2023).

Filipino students generally do well in areas that require higher-order thinking skills, while they suffer in those that do not. According to the 2017–18 Global Competitiveness Report, which ranked the Philippines 79th out of 138 participating nations in terms of high-quality science and mathematics education, the performance of Filipino students in mathematics has to be improved (Schwab, 2018).

Thus, math presents a challenge to students. This could have to do with how the students feel about the subject or how their methods of learning mathematics are influencing their grades. These are only a handful of the inquiries that piqued the curiosity of the researcher and motivated him or her to carry out an analysis and collect information that can support the need for explanations on these persistent enemies (Raba, 2017; Zulaikha, Mansor, Jamaludin & Alias, 2021; Yusuf, Jusoh, & Yusuf, 2019).

One of the vehicles by which mathematics may become interesting is the use of different strategies like instructional modules. An instructional module is a learning material designed primarily for independent or self-study. It may also be used to complement instruction. It has benefits to both teacher and student. For the teacher, the ideal instructional model (instructional module) would make each course both a program of study and a collection of concepts to be internalized through “performance” or “competency–based” activities by the learners. Responsibility for achievement of pre-set goals is placed on the learners. The teacher in such a system coordinates, evaluates, counsels, and guides. Such activities are assumed to enhance the professional status of the teaching role.

The researchers finds it necessary to conduct a study and to find a possible solution like developing an instructional module in Mathematics that will help improve students’ performance. This instructional module which is self-pacing, non-threatening and self-evaluative will serve as supplementary material; which contains necessary exercises that will help enhance the skills learned by the students.

For the students, one purpose of an instructional module is to allow them to proceed at their own rate. The belief that self-pacing is desirable is based on the generally accepted assumption that learners do not achieve at the same rate and are not ready to learn at the same time. Another purpose is to allow the student to choose his learning mode. Choice among different learning modes is desirable if one assumes that learners solve problems and learn using different techniques based on unique behavioral repertoires.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of using instructional modules on the students' mathematics performance in a public mother school in the municipality of Calinog, Iloilo Western Visayas, Philippines.

Specifically, this study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the pre-test mathematics performance of the students in the control group (without instructional module) and the experimental group (with instructional module)?
2. Is there a significant difference in the pre-test mathematics performance of the students in the control group (without instructional module) and the experimental group (with instructional module)?
3. What is the post-test mathematics performance of the students in the control group (without instructional module) and the experimental group (with instructional module)?
4. Is there a significant difference in the post-test mathematics performance of the students in the control group (without instructional module) and the experimental group (with instructional module)?
5. Is there a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mathematics performance of the students in the control group (without instructional module)?
6. Is there a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mathematics performance of the students in the experimental group (with instructional module)?
7. What is the mean gain score in the pre-test and post-test of the students in both control group (without instructional module) and the experimental group (with instructional module)?

METHODOLOGY

This study made use of quasi-experimental research design which involved two sections of Grade 8 learners in a public mother school in the Municipality of Calinog, Province of Iloilo. These two sections were handled by the researchers. Since the study was experimental, one group was assigned as the control group (taught without using instructional module), and another group, was the experimental group (taught with instructional module). To determine the groupings, the researcher used the toss-coin procedure.

In the control group, where the lessons were presented without using the instructional module, the lessons were presented using the following procedures: (a) Presentation of the objectives; (b) Introduction of the Lesson; (c) Giving of Activities - The teacher presents activities for the students to analyze and answer; (d) Analysis - the teacher ask questions for the students to answer that will lead to the understanding of the lesson proper. (e) Assessment - Questions or exercises were given to the students to check their learning of the topic presented; and (f) Assignment - This was a follow-up of what the students had learned and applied what they have learned.

On the other hand, the experimental group taught with instructional modules, the teacher followed the following procedures: (a) Presentation of the objectives; (b) Introduction of the Lesson; (c) Presentation of the Lesson Proper. The teacher gave the instructional modules to each student and each student studied on her/his own and answered the exercises in the instructional module. They were given enough time to work on the exercises and the teacher checked the work of each student.

Instructional Module and Research Instrument

To determine the students' performance in mathematics in the two groups, researcher-constructed forty-item (40) test was used. This was validated and trial tested for reliability.

The researcher also made an instructional module containing all the required competencies for Grade 8 mathematics. These were also presented to the panel of experts for face and content validation. This instructional module was used by the researcher as intervention in the experimental group.

For both instruments, the topics included were in the fourth grading period coverage of the Grade 8 K-12 curriculum. These were: Module 10: Measures of Central Tendency and Measures of Variability; Lesson 1: Measures of Central Tendency for Ungrouped Data; Lesson 2: Measures of Variability; Lesson 3: Measures of Central Tendency for Grouped Data; Lesson 4: Measures of Variability for Grouped Data; Module 11: Introduction to Probability; Lesson 1: Basic Concepts of Probability.

Validity of the Instruments

To establish the validity of the instrument, the researcher submitted the draft of the test and instructional module to the thesis adviser for review, recommendations and suggestions. Then, the drafts were submitted to the panel of experts for face and content validation and inspection of each item for appropriateness, correctness, and meaningfulness of the specific inference. The experts' suggestions, recommendations, and corrections were considered in the refinement of the instruments.

Reliability of the Instrument

Upon the approval of the thesis adviser and panel of experts, the 70-item test was administered for reliability testing to 50 students who belong to one section of the selected school and who were not included in the study. The results underwent item analysis to determine which items would be retained, revised, or rejected. Out of 70 items, 24 items were retained, 30 items were rejected and 16 items were revised.

After retrieval of the accomplished instruments, the data were tabulated and organized. All statistical computations were processed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software.

Data-gathering Procedures

Prior to the actual conduct of the study, the researcher secured permission to conduct the study on the aforementioned school and to use the Grade 8 students as subjects of the study.

After securing the necessary permission, the researcher then personally administered the pre-test to both groups before the start of the grading period and the post test after all the topics had been discussed during the fourth grading period.

The learning competencies and activities were the same for both experimental and control groups. The classes for both sections lasted for one hour per session and were conducted four times a week by the researcher herself. Subjects' attendance during classes was closely monitored to ensure that they completed the study.

The researcher conducted the pre-test at the start of the fourth grading period to both groups. A budgeted outlay was strictly followed and observed. The post-test was conducted by the researcher at the end of the grading period.

Data Analysis

The researcher-made test was reproduced according to the number of subjects of the study. Then the test were administered to the subjects as pre-test and post-test. The tests were corrected and results were analyzed, organized, tabulated, and interpreted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software.

The statistical tools that were used in the study were the frequency count, the mean and Mann-Whitney U test and Wilcoxon Signed-Ranked Test for the inferential analysis.

RESULTS

Pre-test Performance in Mathematics of the Students in the Control Group and the Experimental Group

Results in Table 1 show that the pre-test mathematics performance of the control group ($M = 11.34$) and that of the experimental group ($M = 10.24$) were both satisfactory. A closer look at the results of the both groups showed that the control group obtained a mean score which was a quite higher than that of the experimental group.

Table 1. *Pre-test Mathematics Performance of the Students in the Control Group and the Experimental Group.*

Pre-test	N	Mean	Description
Control Group	53	11.34	Satisfactory
Experimental Group	51	10.24	Satisfactory
Total	104	10.80	Satisfactory

The interpretation was based on the following scale: 30.01 – 40.00 – Outstanding; 20.01 – 30.00 - Very Satisfactory; 10.01 – 20.00 - Satisfactory, and; 0.00 – 10.00 - Fairly Satisfactory.

Significant Difference in the Pre-test Mathematics Performance of the Students in the Control Group and the Experimental Group

To determine any significant difference between the control group and the experimental group’s pre-test mathematics performance, the researcher employed the Mann-Whitney U. As indicated, the computed Z-ratio of -1.952 had a p-value (0.051) higher than the value set at 0.05 level of significance, hence, that the difference is “not significant”.

Table 2. *Significant Difference in the Pre-test Mathematics Performance in Mathematics of the Students in the Control Group and the Experimental Group*

Pre-test	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	Z-ratio	p-value	Remarks
Control Group	53	58.13	1053.00	-1.952	0.051	Not Sig.
Experimental Group	51	46.65				
Total	104					

p > 0.05, not significant

Post-test Mathematics Performance of the Students in the Control Group and the Experimental Group

Results in Table 2 show that the post-test mathematics performance of the control group was “satisfactory” (M = 18.92). On the other hand, the post-test mathematics performance in Mathematics of the experimental group was “ very satisfactory” (M = 23.92).

Table 3. Post-test Mathematics Performance of the Students in the Control Group and the Experimental Group

Pre-test	N	Mean	Description
Control Group	53	18.92	Satisfactory
Experimental Group	51	23.92	Very Satisfactory
Total	104	21.37	Very Satisfactory

The interpretation was based on the following scale: 30.01 – 40.00 – Outstanding; 20.01 – 30.00 - Very Satisfactory; 10.01 – 20.00 - Satisfactory, and 0.00 – 10.00 - Fairly Satisfactory.

Significant Difference in the Post-test Mathematics Performance of the Students in Mathematics in the Control Group and the Experimental Group

To determine the significant difference between the control group’s and experimental group’s post-test mathematics performance, the researcher employed the Mann-Whitney U test. The computed Z-ratio of -3.81 had a p-value (0.000) lower than the value set at 0.05 level of significance, hence, the difference is “significant”.

Table 4. Significant Difference in the Post-test Mathematics Performance of the Students in the Control Group and the Experimental Group.

Pre-test	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	Z-ratio	p-value	Remarks
Control Group	53	41.23	754.00	-3.891	0.000	Significant
Experimental Group	51	64.22				
Total	104					

$p < 0.05$, significant

Significant Difference in the Pre-test and the Post-test Mathematics Performance of Students in the Control Group

To determine the significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mathematics performance of students in the control group, the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test was used. The results revealed that the computed Z-ratio of -5.898^a had a p-value (0.000) lower than the value set at 0.05 level of significance, hence, the difference was “significant”.

Table 5. Significant Difference between the Pre-test and the Post-test Mathematics Performance of the Students in the Control Group

Control Group	Wilcoxon Signed- Rank Test	N	Mean Rank	Z-ratio	p-value	Remarks
Post-test	Negative Ranks	3	9.00	-5.898a	0.000	Significant
Pre-test	Positive Ranks	47	26.55			
	Ties	3				
Total		53				

$p < 0.05$, significant

Significant Difference in the Pre-test and Post-test Mathematics Performance of Students in the Experimental Group

To determine any significant difference in the pre- test and the post-test mathematics performance of students in the experimental group, the researcher used the Wilcoxon Signed- Rank test. The results revealed that the computed Z-ratio of -6.097^a had a p-value (0.000) lower than the value set at 0.05 level of significance, hence the difference is “significant”.

Table 6. Significant Difference in the Pre-test and Post-test Performance in Mathematics of the Students in the Experimental Group

Experimental Group	Wilcoxon Signed- Rank Test	N	Mean Rank	Z-ratio	p-value	Remarks
Post-test	Negative Ranks	0	0.00	-6.097 ^a	0.000	Significant
Pre-test	Positive Ranks	49	25.00			
	Ties	2				
Total		51				

$p < 0.05$, significant

Mean Gain Scores of the Students in the Pre-test and Post-test in both the Control Group (without instructional module) and Experimental Group (with instructional module)

Results in Table 7 show that the main gain score in mathematics of the control group was 7.58), and that of the experimental group was 13.69). A closer look at the results for both groups would show that the control group obtained a mean gain score which is lower than that of the experimental group.

Table 7. Mean Gain Scores of the Students in the Pre-test and the Post-test of Both the Control Group (without instructional module) and the Experimental Group (with instructional module).

Group	N	Mean Gain
Control Group	53	7.58
Experimental Group	51	13.69

DISCUSSION

A closer look at the results of the both groups showed that the control group obtained a mean score which was a quite higher than that of the experimental group. This implies that although there was a slight difference in their mean scores, both are still described as “satisfactory”. This means that their performance was a result of previous knowledge they acquired and is limited such that they fall in the same category.

The control group scored a quite higher than the experimental group and this can be attributed to the learning styles, study habits, and attitudes of the subjects in their previous grade level. This result is consistent with a study on attitudes toward education and study habits conducted in 2019 by Capuno, Necesario, Etcuban, Espina, Padillo, and Manguilimotan. In that study, the researchers found that while the respondents had neutral attitudes toward their motivation, self-confidence, and enjoyment of mathematics, they had positive attitudes toward the subject matter overall. Additionally, the study demonstrates that although there was a weak positive correlation between respondents' academic performance in math and their belief in its value, there was a negligible positive correlation between respondents' attitudes and academic performance in terms of their motivation, enjoyment, and self-confidence. It was determined that attitudes and study habits of students have a major impact on how well they succeed in mathematics.

This implies that although both groups increased their performance, the experimental group (using instructional module) performed much higher than the control group (without using instructional module). Since, the intervention (instructional module) was given to the experimental group, it had a great effect on their mathematics performance.

Although the control group also demonstrated improvement in their post test performance, the results with the experimental group strongly pointed out the beneficial use of the instructional module. The module must have worked effectively to suit to the learners' needs and therefore improved the mathematical competencies of the students. On the other hand, the absence of the instructional module in the control group could be interpreted as one factor that caused them to lag behind the experimental group.

The results further showed that the experimental groups' performance was given a positive impact on the use of the instructional module on the learning processes of the students. The intervention must have provided the students the opportunities to work in their own unique pacing as they went through their lessons, giving them more freedom to think and absorb well the ideas presented. The experimental group's performance shifted from "satisfactory" to "very satisfactory".

This finding is consistent with the theory put forth by Onyedikachi (2011), which was referenced in Oden's study (n.d.), according to which educational resources enable students to get a deeper comprehension of the material and become self-sufficient learners. Additionally, Ezekoka's (2008) study found that generated instructional materials were crucial to the modes of delivery of teaching and learning since they conveyed all pertinent information, data, and signals from the transmitting source—teachers—to the recipient—learners.

The outcome is consistent with the findings of Onasanwa and Omosewo (2011), who talked about instructional materials as a crucial element that may be utilized in the teaching and learning process to spread knowledge, statistics, concepts, and messages that could aid students in improving their academic performance.

The outcome and the research by Utami, Aminatun, and Fatriana (2020) are likewise similar. The data suggest that the use of student workbook offers favorable impact on students' learning since it might be one of the sources of learning besides the teacher's explanation. Additionally, the products' varied techniques and straightforward text help pupils learn them more easily. Ultimately, this study should serve as a helpful resource or manual for future researchers wishing to undertake comparable studies on the usage of student workbooks (LKS) as instructional aids.

Additionally, Susantini et al. (2016) found that using student workbooks (LKS) as a teaching tool has certain benefits for the classroom teaching and learning process. These benefits include making learning more condensed than it would be in textbooks and having a large number of practice questions that are relevant to the material being learned. Additionally, student workbooks can increase academic performance and foster greater student participation and effectiveness. As mentioned, a student workbook helps foster critical thinking abilities. Their performance shifted from "high" to "very high".

The significant difference in the pre-test and post-test results in the mathematics performance of the control group would mean that other factors might have contributed to the better performance of the students. It can also be attributed to the creativity of the mathematics teacher in his methods and approaches in teaching. According to (Sequeira (2012), learning can be considered as change that is permanent in nature because change is brought into students by a teacher through techniques like developing specific skills, changing some attitudes, or understanding specific scientific law operating behind a learning environment. The teacher tends to allow the students to their think further so that they will not be stuck "inside the box".

The teacher encourages the students to become independent in enhancing their thinking skills.

The significant improvement in the mathematics performance of the students in the experimental group can be attributed to the instructional module used as an effective intervention. The result showing the positive effect upon the learners is congruent with the study of Anwar (2017) in which stated that the use of student workbook help students to understand the lessons taught. Besides, this media not only be seen as a tool for teachers to teach but more as a means to convey and channel messages from sources (teachers, books, etc.) to recipients of messages (students learn). The student workbook is like a messenger that is not only used by the teacher as a teaching media but also can be used by the students to help their learning process.

The results provide more evidence in favor of the theory that module-based training can improve students' mathematical ability. Similar to Lim's (2016) study, which examined how word problem solving was taught to college students exposed to both the lecture style and modular training. According to his findings, modular instruction outperformed the conventional lecture style by a wide margin. It is concluded that modular instruction is a successful teaching strategy for teaching math, specifically word problem solving, based on the stated data. Similarly, Madriaga (2004) discovered that using modules allows teachers more time to work one-on-one with pupils. She went on to say that the experimental group that received modular education performed better. Additionally, in Rizaldo, et al. al., (2007), where they came to the conclusion that employing the modular teaching approach improved student performance and subject matter mastery. Hence, the use of the instructional module in mathematics as part of the study is one innovative step toward a better teaching-learning environment for students.

A closer look at the results for both groups would show that the control group obtained a mean gain score which is lower than that of the experimental group. This implies that the big difference in the mean gain scores of the experimental group and the control group could be attributed to the use of instructional module which greatly improved the mathematics performance of the experimental students.

Conclusions

Based on the foregoing results, the following conclusions were formulated:

1. The performance of the subjects in the pre-test is almost the same before the conduct of the study.
2. The instructional module is an effective tool in teaching mathematics which resulted in better performance of the students.
3. The creativity and varied teaching styles of the teacher in teaching also have an impact on students' mathematics learning.

4. Students perform better if they are exposed to materials which they can independently explore, manipulate, and use.

5. Learning is facilitated in self-contained, independent, and self-paced learning activities which are tailored to students' learning styles.

6. Collaborative learning is effectively achieved through the use of instructional module.

Parents' involvement ensures success in students' learning through performance of catch-up lessons in the modules.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are advanced:

1. Teachers should use a variety of teaching strategies and styles in teaching mathematics and not confined themselves to the traditional lecture discussion method.

2. Mathematics teachers should be encouraged to use the instructional module prepared by the researcher in their Mathematics lessons.

3. Classrooms should be equipped with support materials which students can explore, manipulate, and use independently.

4. Learning activities which are self-contained, independent, self-paced, and tailored to the students' learning styles in order to promote an interactive learning environment should be encouraged.

5. Mathematics department/division chairs should develop instructional modules in collaboration with the teachers to facilitate self-learning and provide visual instructional/ review materials to students.

6. Seminar-workshops in the development of instructional modules, workbooks, and other instructional materials should be conducted to equip teachers with skills to develop such materials for their personal and professional growth.

7. A follow-up studies may be conducted using instructional modules for other grading periods, other grade levels, and other subject areas.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study took into consideration the ethical standards in doing research. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their inclusion in the study. Participants were informed about the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Ethical standards also required the researchers to ensure the privacy and confidentiality of the subject being studied. Two standards applied in order to protect the privacy of the research participants. Almost all research guarantees the participants' confidentiality -- they were assured that identifying information would not be made available to anyone who is not directly involved in the study.

The author confirms that this thesis is their own work and that all sources have been appropriately cited. Each author confirms that the work is original and that

appropriate credit has been given to all sources and collaborators to avoid any form of plagiarism.

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